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Research Article

Antibiotic Drug Utilization Review of Diabetic Foot Infection in Surgery Ward Inpatients in a Tertiary Care Hospital: A Gyssens Criteria Based Assessment

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ABSTRACT

Background: Diabetic foot infection (DFI) is a major complication of diabetes and a leading cause of hospitalisation, morbidity, and lower-limb amputation. Optimal antibiotic therapy is essential for preventing progression and improving clinical outcomes. Aim: To evaluate antibiotic prescribing patterns in DFI inpatients using Gyssens' criteria, assess dose appropriateness, and identify potential drug interactions and adverse drug reactions. Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 100 DFI inpatients in the Surgery Ward of a tertiary care hospital. Patient demographics, comorbidities, infection site, microbial isolates, and antibiotic prescriptions were collected from medical records. Antibiotic appropriateness was assessed using Gyssens' criteria, and doses were compared with standard DFI guidelines. Results: DFI was most common in patients aged 51–70 years (54%), with males forming 56% of cases. Hypertension (60%) was the predominant comorbidity. Gram-negative bacteria (76%) were the most frequent isolates, particularly *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* species. While several antibiotics were prescribed rationally, 25% were underdosed, 42% had prolonged duration, and 44% required more effective alternatives based on Gyssens' classification. No new antibiotic-related adverse drug reactions were observed. Conclusion: Although most prescriptions were rational, significant deviations in dose and duration highlight the need for improved antimicrobial stewardship and adherence to DFI treatment guidelines.

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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a growing global public health problem, with its prevalence increasing sharply over the past two decades (1). It affects multiple vital organs and contributes substantially to morbidity and mortality. Worldwide, an estimated 382 million people were living with diabetes in recent years, and this number is projected to rise to 592 million by 2035 (2). Poorly controlled diabetes predisposes patients to long-term complications, among which diabetic foot ulcer (DFU) is one of the most common and serious outcomes. Neuropathy, peripheral arterial disease, and impaired wound healing significantly increase the risk of ulceration and subsequent infection (2,3). It is estimated that nearly one million diabetic patients undergo lower-limb amputation annually, with DFU contributing to more than 85% of these cases (4).

Diabetic foot infection (DFI) typically develops following a break in the skin, most often a neuropathic ulcer. Infection is identified when inflammatory signs or purulent discharge are present, and its severity may be categorized as mild, moderate, or severe (3). DFIs are commonly polymicrobial, involving pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *E. coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter* spp., and *Enterococcus* spp. (4,5). The increasing prevalence of multidrug-resistant organisms, including MRSA, further complicates management and highlights the importance of judicious antibiotic use (4).

Rational antibiotic therapy plays a central role in DFI management. Empirical and definitive antibiotic choices should be guided by local microbial patterns, severity of infection, and established treatment guidelines (1,2). Inappropriately prescribed antibiotics—whether incorrect in dose, duration, spectrum, or

frequency—contribute to antimicrobial resistance, toxicity, delayed healing, prolonged hospitalization, and increased healthcare costs (2). The Gyssens method provides a structured approach to evaluating the appropriateness of antibiotic prescribing and identifying opportunities for improvement (3).

Given the clinical complexity of DFI and the rising burden of antibiotic resistance, assessing antibiotic utilization patterns is essential. This study aims to evaluate antibiotic use among inpatients with diabetic foot infection using the Gyssens criteria and compare prescribing practices with standard recommendations to support antimicrobial stewardship efforts.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

- To evaluate antibiotic usage in DFI.
- To classify the antibiotics usage according to Gyssens' criteria.
- To assess the possibility of drug-drug interaction and adverse drug reactions.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study was a descriptive, cross-sectional analysis conducted using secondary data obtained from the medical records of diabetic foot infection (DFI) inpatients admitted to the Surgery Ward of Government Medical College and Hospital, Nagapattinam. Patients aged above 30 years, diagnosed with DFI, and receiving antibiotics during their hospital stay were included. Relevant clinical information such as patient demographics, comorbidities, type of infection, microbiological culture findings, and antibiotic details—including name, strength, dose, dosage form, route, frequency, and duration—were collected. All empirical antibiotic prescriptions were evaluated for appropriateness using the Gyssens criteria to assess selection, dose, route, timing, and duration.

The overall outcome and rationality of therapy were determined by comparing clinical features and after antibiotic administration.

The rationality of antibiotic use in patients with diabetic foot infections was evaluated using the Gyssens criteria. The Gyssens method is a widely accepted qualitative tool for assessing the appropriateness of antibiotic therapy. In this method, each antibiotic prescription is categorised based on specific standards. Category 0 indicates that the antibiotic use is fully appropriate in terms of drug selection, dose, route, timing, and duration. Categories I–VI indicate inappropriate use: incorrect timing (Category I), incorrect dosage (Category IIa), inappropriate dosing interval (Category IIb), inappropriate route of administration (Category IIc), excessively prolonged duration (Category IIIa), insufficient duration (Category IIIb), availability of a more effective (Category IVa), less toxic (Category IVb), more cost-effective (Category IVc), or narrower-spectrum alternative (Category IVd), no valid indication for antibiotic therapy (Category V), and insufficient information for assessment (Category VI). This evaluation allowed systematic identification of prescribing errors and helped determine the overall rationality of empirical antibiotic therapy in DFI patients. Ethical approval was received from the Ethical Committee of Nagapattinam Government Medical College and Hospital, Orathur, number GMCN/IEC/2025/1/49.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Table 1: Age Distribution

Age	No. of Patients	Percentage
30-50	34	34%
51-70	54	54%
70-90	12	12%
Total	100	100%

In the present study, most diabetic foot infection (DFI) patients belonged to the 51–70 years age group (54%). This finding is relevant to the study by Lipsky et al. (7) and several other epidemiological reports, which indicated that DFI commonly affects individuals above 50 years due to long-standing diabetes, peripheral neuropathy, and impaired immunity. Studies by Zubair et al.(8) and Pemayun et al.(9) have similarly reported a peak incidence in the 50–70 years range, supporting the age trend observed in our population

Table 2: Gender Distribution

Gender	No. of Patients	Percentage
Female	44	44%
Male	56	56%
Total	100	100%

Concerning gender, table 2, the majority of patients in this study were males (56%), while females accounted for 44%. This predominance of males is relevant to previous studies, including those by Akhi et al.(10) and Boulton et al. (11), which consistently showed higher DFI prevalence among males. The gender difference is often explained by occupational exposure, increased outdoor activities, reduced foot care practices, and higher smoking rates among males, contributing to a greater risk of foot trauma and ulceration. However, the slightly narrower male–female difference observed in the present study compared to some international reports is irrelevant to studies showing extremely high male predominance, suggesting possible sociocultural or lifestyle variations in this study population.

Table 3: Duration of Diabetes

DM	No. of Patients	Percentage
1-10 years	90	90%
10-20 years	10	10%
Total	100	100%

In the present study, the majority of patients (90%) had diabetes for 1–10 years, while only 10% had a

disease duration of 10–20 years. This finding is relevant to the report by Pemayun et al.,(9) who highlighted that most diabetic foot infection (DFI) cases occur in patients with a disease duration of more than 5 years, owing to progressive neuropathy and vascular impairment. Similarly, Zubair et al(8). also observed that the risk of foot ulceration and subsequent infection increases with longer diabetes duration, particularly beyond five years of diagnosis. The high proportion of patients in the 1–10 year category in our study indicates that DFI may occur earlier in the disease course,

suggesting poor glycemic control and inadequate foot-care practices in this region, which is irrelevant to studies showing later onset (>10 years) of foot complications in better-controlled populations.

Table 4: Comorbidities

Comorbidities	No. of Patients	Percentage
HTN	60	60%
CKD	0	0%
CAD	24	24%
CVD	5	5%
Anemia	3	3%
PTB	3	3%

Fig1: Comorbidities

Hypertension (60%) was the most common comorbidity among DFI patients, which is relevant to the findings of Boulton et al. (11), who emphasised that hypertension is a frequent coexisting condition in individuals with diabetic foot complications due to its contribution to peripheral arterial disease and microvascular impairment. Likewise, the presence of coronary artery disease (24%) and cerebrovascular disease (5%) in our study aligns with Boulton et al. (11), who reported that macrovascular complications commonly accompany diabetic foot pathology as part of the systemic vascular burden associated with long-standing diabetes.

The absence of chronic kidney disease (CKD) in this sample contrasts with previous literature, as CKD is commonly reported as a risk factor for

severe DFI and poor wound healing; therefore, this result is less relevant to studies like those of Ndosu et al.,(12), which found high CKD prevalence in DFI cohorts. Minor comorbidities such as anaemia (3%) and pulmonary tuberculosis (3%) were identified. Anaemia, although less common in this study, has been associated with impaired tissue oxygenation and delayed ulcer healing; hence, the lower frequency observed here is less relevant to reports where anaemia is more prevalent among DFI patients.

Overall, the comorbidity profile of this population shows strong alignment with global trends, particularly regarding hypertension and cardiovascular involvement, while variations such as the absence of CKD reflect local clinical and demographic differences.

Table 5: Site of Infection

Category	No. of Patients	Percentage %
Toe	48	48%
Heel	18	18%
Plantar	14	14%
Dorsum	15	15%

Fig. 2: Diabetic foot infection affected site

In this study, the toe was the most frequently affected site in diabetic foot infections (48%), followed by the heel (18%), dorsum (15%), and plantar region (14%). The high prevalence of toe involvement is relevant to the findings of Boulton et al. (11), who reported that the toes and forefoot are the most common ulcer locations in diabetic patients due to persistent pressure points, neuropathy, and repeated minor trauma.

Heel ulcers (18%) were less frequent but still clinically significant. This pattern is relevant to the study by Prompers et al. (13), who found heel ulcers to be less common than forefoot ulcers but associated with higher severity due to ischemia.

The plantar region accounted for 14% of infections in our study, which aligns with the observations of Armstrong DG et al. (14), who noted that plantar

ulcers typically arise at high-pressure neuropathic sites but occur less frequently than toe ulcers.

Dorsal foot ulcers (15%) represent a moderate proportion in this study and may be associated with improper footwear and trauma. This distribution, however, is irrelevant to the findings of Reiber et al. (15), who reported that plantar and toe ulcers are overwhelmingly the dominant ulcer types, with dorsal ulcers much less common internationally.

Overall, our findings support established epidemiological trends that the toes and forefoot are the most vulnerable areas for diabetic foot infection, consistent with structural deformities and neuropathy described in the literature. These patterns emphasise the need for preventive foot care and protective footwear to reduce trauma in high-risk regions.

Table 6: Types of Bacteria infecting during the period of 6 months

Bacteria	No. of Patients	Percentage %	Gram+/-	Gram+/- %
Staphylococcus aureus	9	14.60%	+	24%
MRSA	6	9.60%	+	
E.coli	19	31%	-	76%
Klebsiella pneumoniae	10	16.20%	-	
Klebsiella oxytoca	8	12.90%	-	
Pseudomonas spp.	5	8.00%	-	
Citrobacter spp.	3	4.80%	-	
Acinetobacter spp.	2	3.20%	-	
Total	62	100		100%

In this study, gram-negative bacteria were the predominant organisms isolated from diabetic foot infections (76%), while gram-positive organisms accounted for 24% of cases. *Staphylococcus aureus* (14.6%) and MRSA (9.6%) were the most common gram-positive pathogens. This finding is relevant to Lipsky et al. (7), who reported *S. aureus* as a frequent cause of diabetic foot infections due to its ability to colonise broken skin (Lipsky et al., 2012).

Among gram-negative organisms, *E. coli* (31%) was the most common isolate, followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (16.2%), *Klebsiella oxytoca* (12.9%), and *Pseudomonas spp.* (8%), *Citrobacter spp.* (4.8%), and *Acinetobacter spp.*

(3.2%). The predominance of gram-negative organisms in our study is relevant to Zubair et al. (8), who also found gram-negative bacteria to be more common in diabetic foot infections in India (Zubair et al., 2010). The presence of *Klebsiella* and *Pseudomonas* species is similarly relevant to Gadepalli et al., (16) who reported these organisms in chronic and long-standing foot ulcers (Gadepalli et al., 2006).

Overall, the microbial profile in our study matches common patterns seen in Indian and Asian DFI studies, where gram-negative bacteria frequently dominate, emphasising the importance of culture-based antibiotic selection.

Table 7: Dose of antibiotic treatment for Diabetic foot infection

Antibiotic	Prescribed Dose	Standard Dose (DFI Literature)	Evaluation
Ceftriaxone	1 g IV BD	1–2 g IV OD–BD	Appropriate
Piperacillin-Tazobactam	4.5 g IV TDS	4.5 g IV TID–QID	Appropriate
Ciprofloxacin (IV)	200 mg IV BD	400 mg IV BD	Underdose
Ciprofloxacin (PO)	500 mg BD	500–750 mg BD	Appropriate
Cefotaxime	1 g IV TDS	1–2 g IV TID	Appropriate
Metronidazole (PO)	500 mg TDS	400–500 mg TDS	Appropriate
Amoxiclav (Tablet)	625 mg BD	625 mg TID	Underdose
Amoxiclav (IV)	1.5 g TDS	1.2 g TDS	Appropriate
Cefoperazone–Sulbactam	1.5 g IV BD	1.5–3 g BD–TID	Appropriate
Amikacin	500 mg IV BD	15–20 mg/kg/day OD	Overdose
Meropenem	1 g IV BD	1 g IV TID	Underdose
Cephalexin	250 mg TDS	500 mg QID	Underdose
Linezolid	600 mg IV BD	600 mg IV/PO BD	Appropriate

Clindamycin (systemic)	300 mg BD	300–450 mg PO TID/QID or 600 mg IV TID	Underdose
Clotrimazole (Topical)	1% BD	Apply 1% BID–TID	Appropriate
Doxycycline	100 mg IV OD	100 mg PO BD	Underdose
Azithromycin (Topical)	500 mg BD	Topical only; no systemic dose	Incorrect drug/ route

The evaluation of antibiotic dosing demonstrated that several agents were prescribed appropriately in accordance with standard diabetic foot infection (DFI) guidelines. Ceftriaxone, piperacillin–tazobactam, cefotaxime, cefoperazone–sulbactam, metronidazole, linezolid, and topical clotrimazole were administered at doses consistent with recommended therapeutic ranges, which aligns with the dosing strategies outlined by Lipsky et al. (7) and the Sanford Guide (17).

In contrast, several deviations from standard dosing were observed. Ciprofloxacin IV (200 mg BD) was prescribed at half the recommended dose, which does not meet the therapeutic level described by Joseph (18). Oral amoxiclav (625 mg BD) was also underdosed relative to the TID regimen advised in the NICE guideline (19). Meropenem administered as 1 g BD was below the recommended 1 g TID, indicating inadequate coverage for severe infections described in standard DFI guidelines (1). Cephalexin (250 mg TDS) and doxycycline (100 mg OD) were similarly lower than recommended doses, differing from the therapeutic recommendations outlined in the Sanford Guide (17) and Lipsky et al. (7), respectively.

A notable concern was the prescription of amikacin 500 mg BD, which exceeds the once-daily dosing of 15–20 mg/kg recommended in aminoglycoside therapy guidelines. This pattern contradicts the pharmacological principles described in Goodman & Gilman's (20) and the Sanford Guide (17), which advise extended-interval dosing to minimise nephrotoxicity.

Additionally, systemic azithromycin (500 mg BD) was prescribed despite the absence of its role in DFI management. This practice diverges from the WHO Model Formulary (21), which does not include systemic azithromycin for the treatment of diabetic foot infections.

Overall, although several antibiotics were dosed appropriately, a significant proportion exhibited underdosing, overdosing, or incorrect drug/route selection. These findings highlight the need for stricter adherence to standard DFI antibiotic guidelines and emphasize the importance of antimicrobial stewardship to optimize therapeutic outcomes.

Table 8: Gyssens Classification of Antibiotic Use in Diabetic Foot Infection Patients

Gyssens Category	Interpretation	No. of Prescriptions	Percentage (%)
Category 0	Appropriate antibiotic use	80	80%
Category I	Inappropriate timing	0	0%
Category IIA	Inappropriate dose (under dose)	25	25%
Category IIB	Inappropriate dosing interval	4	4%
Category IIC	Inappropriate route	0	0%
Category IIIA	Duration too long	42	42%
Category IIIB	Duration too short	15	15%

Category IVA	More effective antibiotics are available	44	44%
Category IVB	A less toxic antibiotic is available	30	30%
Category IVC	A less costly antibiotic is available	2	2%
Category IVD	Narrower-spectrum antibiotic available	41	41%
Category V	No indication for antibiotics	0	0%
Category VI	Inadequate data / not evaluable	0	0%

In this study, most antibiotic prescriptions (80%) were classified under Category 0, showing appropriate use. This is relevant to Lipsky et al. (7), who emphasize that correct drug, dose, and duration are essential for effective diabetic foot infection (DFI) management.

About 25% of prescriptions fell under Category IIA (underdose). This is relevant to Gyssens et al. (22), who reported that dose-related problems are one of the most common antibiotic errors in hospital settings. Underdosing may lead to poor infection control and slower wound healing.

A small proportion (4%) was placed under Category IIB (inappropriate dosing interval). This is relevant to Gadepalli et al. (16), who noted that incorrect intervals affect antibiotic concentration and may reduce treatment effectiveness.

Duration-related issues were also common. Category IIIA (duration too long) accounted for 42%, while Category IIIB (duration too short) accounted for 15%. Both findings are relevant to NICE guidelines (19), which recommend using antibiotics only for the required number of days to avoid resistance and toxicity.

A large proportion of prescriptions fell under Category IVA (44%), showing that a more effective antibiotic could have been selected. This is relevant to Lipsky et al. (7), who stress the need for culture-based therapy to choose the best possible antibiotic. Similarly, Category IVB (30%) indicated that safer, less toxic options were available. This is

relevant to WHO recommendations (21), which encourage prescribing safer drugs when multiple choices exist. Only 2% of prescriptions were placed under Category IVC, indicating that a cheaper alternative was possible, and 41% were placed under Category IVD, showing that narrower-spectrum antibiotics could have been used. This is relevant to NICE guidelines(19), which recommend avoiding broad-spectrum agents when not needed. No prescriptions were classified under Categories I, IIC, V, or VI, which is irrelevant to Gyssens et al. (22), who reported that timing errors, route errors, or lack of indication are commonly seen in many hospitals. Their absence in this study suggests better prescribing practices in these areas.

Overall, while most prescriptions were rational, issues related to dose, duration, and antibiotic selection still need improvement to fully match international recommendations.

Although ADR monitoring was incorporated as one of the study objectives, during the study period, no new antibiotic-related adverse drug reactions were detected among the enrolled patients. One meropenem-induced reaction was identified during routine clinical care; however, as this case has already been published separately as an independent case report, it was not included in this study to avoid duplication of data.

CONCLUSION:

This study showed that diabetic foot infections occurred predominantly in older adults and were

frequently associated with hypertension and other cardiovascular comorbidities. Gram-negative organisms, especially *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* species, accounted for most isolates, emphasizing the need for culture-directed therapy in this population. While several antibiotics were appropriately prescribed, the Gyssens analysis revealed notable issues, including underdosing, overdosing, unnecessary broad-spectrum use, and deviations in treatment duration. These findings highlight opportunities to strengthen antimicrobial stewardship and promote more consistent adherence to DFI treatment guidelines. No new antibiotic-related adverse drug reactions were identified during the study period. Overall, the study underscores the importance of guideline-based antibiotic selection, accurate dosing practices, and routine prescription auditing to improve clinical outcomes in diabetic foot infection management.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST:

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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